

COMPARISON OF COUNTABLE AND UNCOUNTABLE NOUNS IN ENGLISH AND RUSSIAN LANGUAGES

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Annotation. The article describes the category of countability and uncountability of English and Russian nouns. The analyzed material shows that there are both similarities and differences in the expression of this category between English and Russian literature. We exert to compare and contrast the approaches in each language.

Key words: noun, countable, uncountable, similarities, compare.

Аннотация: В статье описаны категории исчисляемых и неисчисляемых английских и русских существительных. Проанализированный материал показывает, что в выражении этой категории между английской и русской литературой имеются как сходства, так и различия. Мы постараемся сравнить и противопоставить подходы на каждом языке.

Ключевые слова: существительное, исчисляемое, неисчисляемое, сходство, сравнение.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada ingliz va rus tillaridagi otlarning sanaladigan va sanalmaydigan toifasi tasvirlangan. Tahlil qilingan material shuni ko'rsatadiki, bu turkumni ifodalashda ingliz va rus adabiyoti o'rtasida ham o'xshashlik, ham farqlar mavjud. Biz har bir tildagi yondashuvlarni solishtirish va taqqoslashga harakat qilamiz.

Kalit so'zlar: ot, sanaladigan, sanalmaydigan, o'xshashlik, qiyoslash.

A noun is a word that identifies a person, place, object, or concept. In a sentence, nouns can function as the subject, direct object, indirect object, subject complement, object complement, appositive, or modifier.¹

Common nouns can be divided into two groups: countable (исчисляемые) and uncountable (неисчисляемые).

1 K.N.Kachalova, E.E.Israilevich. English grammar. Bishkek 2006, 10 p

1. Countable nouns are names of objects that can be counted. They are used in the singular, as well as in the plural.²

Теперь года прошли. – Now the years have passed Я в возрасте ином. – I am at a different age.

И чувствую и мыслю по-иному. – And I feel and think differently

И говорю за праздничным вином: - And I say over celebratory wine Хвала и слава рулевому! – Praise and glory to the helmsman³

2. Uncountable nouns are names of objects that can not be counted. They are material and abstract nouns, which used only in singular form⁴

Последняя туча рассеянной бури! – The last cloud of the scattered storm Одна ты несешься по ясной лазури, - You alone rush across the clear azure Одна ты наводишь унылую тень, - You alone cast a sad shadow⁵

Одна ты печалишь ликующий день - You alone sadden the jubilant day

3. Some material nouns can be used, as in Russian, to denote an object or objects made of a given substance or material; in this case, they become countable nouns⁶

He carried a brick (two bricks) in each hand Он нес кирпич (два кирпича) в каждой руке.

4. Abstract nouns become countable nouns when they are specified⁷ He made a speech yesterday - His speeches are always interesting Он произнес вчера речь - Его речи всегда интересны⁸

Most uncountable nouns are singular, but a few are plural. These include clothes, scissors, jeans, spectacles, trousers, groceries, etc. With these words, we use a plural verb.⁹

Oh, no! My new clothes are dirty!

О, нет! Моя новая одежда грязная!¹⁰

2 K.N.Kachalova, E.E.Israilevich. English grammar. Bishkek 2006, 10 p

3 Sergey Esenin, Letter to woman, Saint Petersburg, 1924, 25 p

4 K.N.Kachalova, E.E.Israilevich. English grammar. Bishkek 2006, 10 p

5 Alexander Pushkin, Cloud, 1835, 75 p

6 K.N.Kachalova, E.E.Israilevich. English grammar. Bishkek 2006, 11 p

7 K.N.Kachalova, E.E.Israilevich. English grammar. Bishkek 2006, 11 p

8 Jane Austin, Pride and Justice, London, 19th, 55 p

9 Malcolm Mann, Steve Taylore-Knowles. Destination B2. London 2005, 43 p

10 Vladimir Novikov, Lolita, Moskow, 2003, 46 p

Some nouns are countable with one meaning and uncountable with another meaning¹¹

Do you think you could bring me a clean glass? (countable)¹²

Как думаешь, ты мог бы принести мне чистый стакан? (исчисляемое) We should make computer monitors out of recycled glass (uncountable)¹³

Нам следует делать компьютерные мониторы из переработанного стекла (неисчисляемое)

Using a, the, some, many with countable nouns. Also we can use a singular or plural verb.

Where is the newspaper? - Где газета?¹⁴

How many channels do you get? – Сколько каналов у вас есть?

There are common uncountable nouns in English and Russian language: advice, coffee, furniture, glass, hair, homework, information, knowledge, luggage, money, news, paper, work.

She gave me a useful advice – Она мне дала полезный совет¹⁵

In conclusion, it should be mentioned that grammar of English and Russian languages are similar. We compared countable and uncountable nouns in English and Russian, and we also studied the use of definite and indefinite articles and looked through at the main uncountable nouns in both languages.

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